

Easy Read: Government Grants and Fairness – 2025

This is a simple guide to help people understand how fair some Australian government grants were in 2025. These grants gave money to small businesses, apprentices, and childcare services. We looked at who the grants helped, who they left out, and how they could be made better and fairer for everyone.

1. Business Basics Grant – Queensland

What is it? - Gives \$7,500 to small businesses for things like websites, marketing, and business advice.

What's not fair? - Doesn't include support for hiring people with disabilities or from diverse backgrounds. - Doesn't give help with things like making businesses more accessible. - No special help for businesses run by Aboriginal, Torres Strait Islander, disabled, or queer people.

How to make it better: - Let businesses use the money for inclusion and accessibility. - Give extra points to businesses led by people who face barriers. - Make the forms and process easier to understand and access.

2. Small Business Apprenticeship Pilot – Queensland

What is it? - Helps small businesses pay apprentice wages while they are training. - Only for jobs in construction, plumbing, electrical, and engineering.

What's not fair? - Focuses on jobs that mostly men do. - Doesn't encourage hiring young people from different backgrounds. - First-come, first-served model makes it harder for businesses in rural areas or without internet access.

How to make it better: - Support apprenticeships in jobs like caring, IT, and green jobs. - Help businesses hire apprentices who need more support. - Offer help with things like transport, mentoring, or mental health.

3. Workforce Connect HR Grants – Queensland

What is it? - Offers up to \$5,000 for small businesses to get help with HR (Human Resources) – how they hire and keep staff.

What's not fair? - Doesn't say who "underused groups" are. - No rules to make sure the help really changes things. - Could just be for show, not real change.

How to make it better: - Say clearly which groups are meant to be helped. - Fund ideas made with community or staff input. - Ask for proof that the business is becoming more fair and inclusive.

4. Inclusion Agency Services Tender – National

What is it? - The Australian Government is looking for groups to help childcare services include all children.

What's not fair? - Doesn't require leaders with disability or community knowledge. - Community voices are not included in decision-making. - May only go to big groups, not local or smaller ones.

How to make it better: - Make sure First Nations, disability-led, and diverse groups are part of the work. - Use fairer ways to pick which groups get the job. - Make sure kids and families feel safe, included, and listened to.

In Short

These government grants can help—but only if they include everyone. That means thinking about who gets left out, making things accessible, and asking the people most affected what they need. Fair funding means giving everyone a real chance—not just the people who already have power.

This guide is for anyone who wants government money to be shared more fairly.